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Social security of the individual and society in the framework of the national security of Ukraine

The article is devoted to the study of the current state of the level of social security of the individual and society in Ukraine. It was noted that social security is one of the important problems that must be resolved in the framework of achieving national security of the state. The criteria for determining social security and their level in Ukraine at the present stage of state development are investigated.

The article reveals the basic concepts of social security of a person, describes the main indicators of social security and the existing problems associated with their achievement.

Keywords: *social security, society, threats to national security, social structure of society, social mobility*

For the modern world today, it is important to harmoniously combine the security of each individual or social group and the whole society. This feature combination is the responsibility. State security policy is based on national security, and due to significant changes and the realities of life requires a complete review.

Today, we include economic security, the state's defense, protection against man-made and environmental disasters, and social security as part of national security. That is why social security should not be ignored in our time, since it plays one of the main functions in the system of national security. Each component of such security cannot be considered separately, since they are interconnected.

If we form the definition of social security, it should be noted that it is a set of measures for protecting the interests of the state and the people in the social sphere, ensuring the development of the social structure and relations in society, the life support system and socialization of people, as well as their way of life depending on factors of progress, present and future generations.

The state of social security, as one of the components of national security, is extremely relevant for Ukraine at the present stage. An objective diagnosis of the social status of the Ukrainian society suggests that the main social risks - poverty, property differentiation of the population, the alienation of a significant number of citizens from public life, the restriction of their access to education, medicine and culture - have reached scales that may pose a real threat to the national security of the state.

Important theoretical, methodological and practical problems of ensuring social security are revealed in the writings of the following authors: A. Novikova, P. Shevchuk, V. Skurativsky, E. Libanova, S. Pirozhkova, O. Bilorus, V. Serebrnikova, V. Danilishina, V. Kutsenko and others.

So, V.N. Nazarkina notes that the approach to solving social and economic problems from the point of view of human development implies a shift in priorities. With such changes, according to the author, not a person should be used to achieve economic goals, and the economy - in the interests of human development. Not a

person - for the protection of state borders, but a state - for the protection of human interests, the creation and use of the benefits of development that are achieved through social solidarity [4].

D.I. Akimov notes that social security is much more a category of national security component on which the state of security of an individual, social group, and society as a whole depends on possible threats to their lives, rights and freedoms. In the end, social security is a caring attitude of the state to its main wealth, that is, a person [1].

The purpose of the article is to determine the main indicators of the social security of an individual and society, as an integral part of the overall national security of Ukraine.

The key feature of the modern stage of development of society through a conflict situation in the state and the government's emphasis on other needs is the departure from socialization of all spheres of human life and submission to their social goals, although a sample of socially and economically developed countries leads to the creation of a social state model. Thus, state and local authorities are called upon to create the necessary conditions for the formation of a welfare state.

The welfare state is a special type of highly developed state, in which a high level of social protection of all citizens is ensured through active work on regulating the social and economic spheres of society, establishing social justice and solidarity in it. Social justice is a philosophical multifaceted and to a certain extent subjective category, which today does not have an unequivocal interpretation, which is closely related to the concepts of "freedom", "social responsibility", and "equality", which form the basis for the formation of a social state.

The concept of "social security" in the scientific literature has been studied, but it has not found a corresponding development in the system of social policy and national security of Ukraine. The Law of Ukraine "On the Fundamentals of National Security" defines security as the security of vital interests of a person, citizen, society

and state, which ensures the sustainable development of society, the timely identification, prevention and neutralization of real and potential threats to national interests.

Scientists interpret the concept of "social security" in different ways:

- the state of life, provided a complex of organizational, legal and economic measures aimed at the realization of social interests, the formation of a favorable demographic situation, the preservation of the state gene pool and the transformation of labor resources in accordance with market requirements;

- the state of guaranteed legal and institutional protection of the vital interests of an individual and society against external and internal threats;

- a set of measures to protect the interests of the state and the people in the social sphere, the development of the social structure and relations in society, the system of life support and socialization of people, lifestyle in accordance with the needs of progress, current and future generations;

- it is positively regulated by legal norms and the state is realized in practice when the state provides the democratic methods of management at its disposal to maintain a decent standard of living for citizens and guarantees the possibility of satisfying the basic needs of its development [5].

In our opinion, today social security is the security of vital interests of a person, citizen, society, timely detection, prevention and neutralization of threats to national interests in the social sphere, which ensures an adequate standard of living of the population, expanded reproduction, development of society and social progress in society.

Typical threats in the social sphere are also defined by the Law of Ukraine "On the Fundamentals of the National Security of Ukraine" and in the "Strategy of the National Security of Ukraine":

- the discrepancy between the programs for reforming the state's economy and the results of their implementation to certain social priorities;

- the ineffectiveness of the state policy to increase the labor income of citizens, overcoming poverty and balancing the productive employment of the able-bodied population;

- the crisis of the health care system and social protection of the population and, as a result, a dangerous deterioration in the health of the population;

- the spread of drug addiction, alcoholism, social diseases;

- aggravation of the demographic crisis;

- population decline due to the deterioration of its health, low quality of life, insufficient birth rate, high mortality, as well as the outflow of citizens of Ukraine abroad

- the growing shortage of labor resources, population aging, low economic activity and the underestimation of the real cost of labor;

- reducing the opportunities for quality education for the poor;

- manifestations of moral and spiritual degradation of society;

- the growth of child and adolescent neglect, homelessness, vagrancy.

In modern research on social security issues, at least four main criteria for assessing social security are distinguished. The social security system of a state is offered to be judged by its abilities, namely:

- prevention of a social explosion situation;

- prevention of degradation of the social structure (both its leveling and the development of the processes of polarization, marginalization and lumpenization)

- ensuring the sustainability of the social structure with normal vertical and horizontal social mobility;

- support of the adequacy of the system of value orientations and culture of social behavior, including political and economic.

The situation of the potential possibility of a social explosion occurs with the simultaneous release of several important parameters of social sustainability beyond the permissible limits. This is a situation in which further movement of society can go

on fundamentally different trajectories with a relatively small external impact. Either an uncontrollable explosion can occur, sweeping away the entire social structure and introducing the state into a state of chaos, or a transition to a new social structure with a subsequent movement of social development along an ascending one. The choice of the trajectory largely depends on the presence of the appropriate political forces that have the necessary political will and a broad social base. The degradation of the social structure is a more complex and time-consuming process. It can flow in two directly opposite directions. On the one hand, leveling of the structure is possible, general leveling. This process usually takes place in the course of major revolutionary upheavals that sweep away the old elites and bring down the pyramid of social stratification [3].

Today, we have a situation in which the old elite executions are dropped and expropriated, and the new ones have not yet had time to form. In the absence of entrenched elites, the continuity of traditions disappears, the identification of their group interests with the interests of the nation, the cultural skills of many generations are lost, the personal ties that underlie management are destroyed, and incentives and initiatives to work and entrepreneurship are undermined.

On the other hand, in the depths of society, a new social structure and new social strata are gradually being formed. The danger is that this can disrupt the normal processes of social mobility. Many of the best representatives of the old elites are dying in the struggle or moving away from vigorous activity, and the much worse representatives of the lower strata are going up the shift on the social ladder.

The polarization of the social structure can have even harder consequences, when a deep failure occurs between the higher strata and the majority of the population. This failure occurs at the place where the middle strata are located in the normal social structure. A so-called bipolar, bimodal or double-humped structure of society arises. It tends, as a rule, to further deepen and leads to an increase in social tensions with a high potential probability of a social explosion.

No less socio-political, its dangerous economic consequences. The middle strata form the source of effective demand that underlies economic growth in a market or mixed economy. In the absence of these layers there is no mass demand - the development of the domestic market is firmly blocked.

At the same time, the market is segmented: on the one hand, an elite market of mainly expensive high-quality imported goods is formed, and on the other hand, a market of low-grade cheap goods, which is mainly satisfied with imports. The stagnation of the economy leads to a crisis of investment activity. The capitals that are accumulated by the elite strata of society go abroad, domestic production drops even more, the number of jobs is reduced, the incomes of the majority of the population are declining, the process acquires an unauthorized character. At a certain stage of this process, such phenomena as marginalization and lumpenization develop [7].

Marginalization is connected with the fact that an increasing number of people are being squeezed out of their social burden, mostly downward and at the same time losing their sustainable lifestyle and activities. The so-called left hump of the bimodal distribution of wealth is increasing more and more. Marginals reduce the level of professionalism and work motivation. The deepening of the gap between them and the upper layers deprives them of their life prospects.

Lumpen - people living on the verge of physiological survival, have practically no durable goods necessary for a normal lifestyle, are roofed over their heads, are denied access to life-saving public consumption funds, produce their own subculture, which is characterized by dependency and aversion to productive work. The extreme form of the process of marginalization is the so-called total (total) marginalization, in which none of the social strata has a stable social burden, including the highest elite executions [6].

In addition, the processes of social mobility acquire a chaotic nature, the mechanism for selecting the best, transferring traditions and cultural skills to new generations ceases to function. The situation of total marginalization generates the

criminalization of society. If it is impossible to secure mobility upwards through socially useful activities, then the path to socially harmful activities remains open. The erosion of normal social structures is accompanied by the multiplication of criminal structures. The basis of the existence of the state is destroyed - the collection of taxes. For people with problems, the state is no longer able to provide legal and police protection to society. A person deprived of state protection is seeking protection for organized crime. One should not hope that with time organized crime will begin to create the rule of law and turn its eyes and capital to production. The very nature of organized crime lies in the fact that it draws monopoly superprofits from offenses, appropriating the functions of state bodies in the field of tax collection, arbitration, and the use of force. Violence ceases to be the monopoly of the state and becomes an instrument of competing criminal clans. The principle of ownership is violated in any form - public, state, collective, private [3].

Social mobility plays a crucial role in maintaining social structure. A well-functioning social mobility turns an ossified social order into a living and flexible social structure. The state of social mobility has a significant impact on the formation of a system of value orientations and social consciousness.

If for the most talented of the lower strata the legal way to the upper strata is open, then this contributes to their orientation towards stability and law and order. If the legal path is difficult, then for them there remains either a struggle against the existing social system, or a departure to criminal structures.

Social mobility has a definite connection with the life cycle of an individual. Gradual ascent over the years, and then security in an unworkable age, create a vital orientation towards sustainability, contribute to strengthening work morale and motivation, a collective orientation related to taking care of a state, a city, a native enterprise. On the contrary, the rapid ascent of the young and, just as quickly going down summer, create an orientation on quick success at any cost, unprincipled. Individual values prevail - the desire to ensure personal success and personal well-

being at any cost. The small category of prosperous, rich arises against the background of the poor majority. The bipolar structure of society determines the formation of a special subculture of poverty, associated with the realization of the impossibility of getting up, with a focus on asocial forms of behavior. On the other hand, the inhibition of the processes of social mobility and the lag of its pace from the life cycle also gives negative consequences in the form of stagnation of the social structure. The dominance of older age groups in the upper echelons of the ruling elite leads to gerontocracy, carrying a number of negative consequences for the entire society.

Under the conditions of a social explosion, normal forms of social mobility are destroyed, the gradual process of leaving the less capable and replacing them with more capable ones is accomplished by an instantaneous massive influx of representatives of the lower strata, which sweeps away the old elite strata. In this stream, the proportion of the criminal element increases sharply, especially during periods when economic decline is accompanied by the flourishing of speculative activity. Disrupted age sequence of social mobility. The latter loses touch with the life cycle. The result is a rapid degradation of the social structure. In the upper echelons the level of culture, education and professionalism falls. In the lower echelons, the subculture of poverty is rapidly developing, with corresponding consequences.

The system of value orientations corresponds to what is called “good” and “bad” in society. It provides answers to the question about attitudes towards life and death, the Motherland, the family, material well-being and spiritual values, a collective or individualistic principle, culture, traditions, history, education, science. In a normal society, there is a more or less unified, common, historically established system of value orientations, from which the value orientations of individual classes, strata, and social groups emerge. Role expectations, domestic, social, political and economic behavior follow from the system of value orientations. In a split society, the system of value orientations is destroyed, contributing to the further disintegration of society. The destruction and disintegration of the system of value orientations contributes to the

development of distemper, difficulties in establishing at least the minimum degree of trust between people and social groups.

The widespread use of a system of indicators at the structural and functional level of the study of economic security actualizes the problem of criteria for assessing the state of security and the form of the limiting values of safety parameters. Note the examples of the limit values of the most important indicators of social security of the state.

Table 1 - Limit values of social security indicators [2]

Social Security Indicator	Limit Value
share in the population of citizens with incomes below the subsistence minimum	7%
life expectancy - 70 years, gap between incomes of 10% of the most profitable and 10% of socially vulnerable groups of population	8 times
limit value according to the unemployment rate	10-12%
GDP per capita	50% of the average for the "seven" and 100% of the average world GDP.

The real position of compliance of individual indicators of social security of Ukraine with its limit value is shown in the following graph.

Fig. 1. Indicators of Ukraine's social security by 2018 [2]

Thus, we see that GDP per capita: from the level of developed countries in Ukraine is at the level of 10.1%, while the threshold value should reach 50%, and GDP per capita from the world average level - 13.2% of limit 100%.

Regarding the indicator “The gap between cash incomes is 10% of the majority and 10% of the poorest groups of the population”, now it is 13%, and its limit value is within 8%.

Such a representative as “The share of the population with income below the poverty line (for cash)” is currently at the level of 53.2% compared with the marginal 7%, and the unemployment rate in our state is 11%.

Complementing the picture of the unsatisfactory state of social security is such figures: according to experts of the Council for the Study of Productive Forces of Ukraine NAS, in 2018 about 5% of the population used up to 30% of funds that were mostly of shadow or criminal origin. At the same time, 25% of the population of Ukraine used only 8% of the funds. According to official statistical information, the share of the cost of food in the cost structure for 2010-2018 has almost doubled and reached 64%. For economically developed countries, the situation with spending one third of the family budget on food is considered a poverty threshold. For comparison, we note that, according to various estimates, in the corresponding period in the United States, the share of expenditures on food in the total cash income was 15-25%, France - 13-25%, Germany - 32%, Japan - 24%.

Thus, the limiting values of social security indicators are considered as limiting values, the non-observance of which impedes the normal development of various elements of reproduction, leads to the formation of negative, destructive tendencies in the social sphere. It is important to emphasize that the highest security measure is achieved under the condition that the whole set of indicators is within the permissible limits of its limit values, and satisfactory values of one indicator are achieved not to the detriment of others. At the same time, indicators of social security acquire the properties of an indicator of socio-economic phenomena and processes.

Analysis of threats to social security allows to draw conclusions about the advantage of threats to the growth of social tension, the deterioration of the demographic situation, the decline in economic activity. The subjects of ensuring social security affect the objects of social security, using a set of methods, levers, tools to overcome threats to national interests in the social sphere and to realize priorities of social interests, based on the principles of ensuring social security and using the norms of the current legal framework, because social security provided by a balanced social policy in accordance with the established in the prescribed ke doctrines, concepts, strategies and programs.

Modern diagnostics of the level of social security necessitates the development of a safety research methodology. In particular, there is a growing need for wider implementation of optimization methods, analysis and processing of scenarios, methods of fuzzy systems theory, specific methods for identifying trends and the level of social security. Along with the methods of observing the main macroeconomic indicators, assessing the rate of economic growth of the state, methods for describing the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the processes that are being researched, they should form a common methodology for studying social security that can quickly respond to the dynamics of scientific knowledge.

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